

Savremena psihijatrija i medicina / Contemporary Psychiatry & Medicine

2021: 3(1), str./pp. 46 – 55

UDK: 615.851:316.6(4-12)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5208014

Primljeno/received: 09.07.2021.

Prihvaćeno/accepted: 10.08.2021.

Short communication

SCALE OF NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL AND PSYCHIATRIC SYMPTOMS OF THE POST- COVID-19 SYNDROME (SNP-PC19): A PILOT STUDY

Selman Repišti

Clinical Center of Montenegro, Podgorica, Montenegro
selman9r@yahoo.com

Lidija Injac Stevović

Corresponding author

Faculty of Medicine, University of Montenegro;
Clinical Center of Montenegro, Podgorica, Montenegro
injacl19@gmail.com

Tamara Radojičić

Clinical Center of Montenegro, Podgorica, Montenegro
tamararadojicic11@gmail.com

Abstract

We present here a new tool designed to measure the severity of neuropsychological and psychiatric symptoms within the so-called "post-COVID-19 syndrome" or "long COVID-19". Based on the relevant literature

as well as clinical experience of the authors, 13 classes of symptoms have been identified. These became the items of the tool entitled "Scale of neuropsychological and psychiatry symptoms of the post-COVID-19 syndrome" (SNP-PC19). This is a five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 0 ("not at all") to 4 ("very strongly") and serving as a measure of the severity of symptoms. The SNP-PC19 was administered online, along with some clinically relevant questions and those aimed at collecting sociodemographics of participants. Fifty-four people answered and the main improvement of the scale was the addition of two items: "losing patience/temper easily" and "frequent and/or sudden mood swings". The version of the scale after the pilot study has thus 15 items. It should be highlighted that its psychometric properties have yet to be examined.

Key words: post-COVID-19 syndrome, long COVID-19, pilot study, scale construction, clinical neuropsychology

INTRODUCTION

As of July 8, 2021, over 184 million cases and over four million deaths due to COVID-19 infection have been detected and confirmed (World Health Organisation, 2021). According to the same source, over three billion vaccine doses have been administered (WHO, 2021).

In parallel, researchers with various backgrounds have been trying to shed light on various aspects of the COVID-19 pandemic. One of the research contributions includes the identification, recognition, and description of the post-COVID-19 syndrome. For example, Salamanna and her colleagues (2021) analysed 145 papers on long-term COVID-19 symptoms and identified three clusters of such symptoms: problems with lung function, neurological (including olfactory) problems, and widespread long-term symptoms (e.g. fatigue and pain). The post-COVID-19 syndrome overlaps with the long-COVID-19, which includes signs and symptoms not attributable to other causes and persistent four weeks after the diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 infection (Sisó-Almirall et al., 2021).

Our work was focused on neuropsychological and psychiatric symptoms of the post-COVID-19 syndrome: working memory dysfunction, problems with

divided attention, difficulties in set-shifting, and lower processing speed (Jaywant et al., 2021); working memory issues, verbal learning problems, and cognitive impairment in general (Miskowiak et al., 2021); depression and sleep problems such as insomnia (Huang et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021), anxiety, depression, insomnia, posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and obsessive-compulsive disorder (Mazza et al., 2020), etc.

METHODS

Scale development procedure

The items included in the scale are actually neuropsychological and psychiatric symptoms that could occur within the post-COVID-19 syndrome. These symptoms have been derived from recently published literature as well as from the authors' clinical experience with people in remission after the COVID-19 infection. Thirteen symptoms have been identified (the first 13 items of the scale in Appendices I & II) and administered online (via Google Forms), in the form of a scale. The study started on April 17, 2021 and finished on July 8, 2021. This was an intentional sampling, because all participants should have had COVID-19 infection.

Sample and instruments

Fifty-four participants gave their opinion about the scale items, answered additional questions related to sociodemographics (gender, age, country of residence, and level of education) and provide some clinically relevant information. The questions used for gathering the additional data were:

- (1) "When did you get COVID-19 infection?"
- (2) "When did you stop feeling the main symptoms of COVID-19 infection, e.g. fever, headache, respiratory problems, etc.?"
- (3) "Have you been treated for a psychiatric, neurological or other illness before getting infected with COVID-19?". Participants' characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sociodemographics and some clinical characteristics of participants

Variables	Descriptives
<i>Gender</i>	
Males	41
Females	13
<i>Age</i>	
M (SD)	37.78 (10.96)
Range	18-61
<i>Country of residence</i>	
Montenegro	28
Bosnia and Herzegovina	16
Serbia	4
Croatia	3
North Macedonia	1
Sweden	1
Austria	1
<i>Level of education</i>	
Secondary education	11
Post-secondary education (2 years)	3
Post-secondary education (4+ years)	40
<i>Got COVID-19 infection</i> (how many days ago)	
M (SD)	148.54 (91.65)
Range	4 – 365
<i>Stopped feeling main COVID-19 symptoms</i> (how many days ago)	
M (SD)	124.49 (90.84)
Range	2 – 350
<i>Treated for illnesses before COVID-19</i>	
No	45
Yes	9

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There were two symptoms not covered by the pilot version of the scale - "losing patience/temper easily" and "frequent and/or sudden mood swings", which are added to the scale. Other symptoms were mostly of a neurological nature (e.g. paraosmia and parageusia – qualitative changes of the smell and taste) or were the same as those in the scale; however, listed by the participants in terms of their synonyms or in the form of a brief explanation (but in different wording compared to that used in the scale by its authors).

It is also noteworthy to mention that the average time from getting COVID-19 infection until participating in this study was approximately five months (148.54 days) whereas the average time passed from the cessation of the main COVID-19 symptoms was around four months (124.49 days). In addition, a great proportion of participants ($n = 45$) had not been treated for other illnesses, before they got infected with the COVID-19. The rest of the participants had been treated mostly for anxiety and depression.

The outcome of the pilot study was the 15-item scale which was enclosed below in English (Appendix I) as well as in Montenegrin/Serbian/Bosnian/Croatian (Appendix II). The scores on the scale are calculated as follows:

- (1) By summing up the participant's score on each item and divide that result by 15; the scores will range from 0 to 4 (in this case, the SNP-CP19 is a measure of severity of symptoms, i.e. severity index),
- (2) By recoding the participant's score on each item (zeros remain zeros; however, scores 1, 2, 3, and 4 will be coded as 1) and summing them up; the scores will range from 0 to 15 (in this way, the total score would represent the total number of neuropsychological and psychiatric symptoms reported by a participant/patient).

Further research is needed for checking the scale's reliability (primarily internal consistency) and validity (in the first place – factor validity which will reveal the latent structure/space of the post-COVID-19 syndrome), as well as its cross-cultural potential for application i.e. usefulness along with its content validity within other cultural settings.

REFERENCES

- Huang, C., Huang, L., Wang, Y., Li, X., Ren, L., Gu, X., Kang, L., Guo, L., Liu, M., Zhou, X., Luo, J., Huang, Z., Tu, S., Zhao, Y., Chen, L., Xu, D., Li, Y., Li, C., Peng, L., Li, Y., Xie, W., Cui, D., Shang, L., Fan, G., Xu, J., Wang, G., Wang, Y., Zhong, J., Wang, C., Wang, J., Zhang, D., Cao, B. (2021). 6-month consequences of COVID-19 in patients discharged from hospital: a cohort study. *Lancet*, 397, 220-232. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32656-8.
- Jaywant, A., Vanderlind, W.M., Alexopoulos, G.S., Fridman, C.B., Perlis, R.H., & Gunning, F.M. (2021). Frequency and profile of objective cognitive deficits in hospitalized patients recovering from COVID-19. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, doi:10.1038/s41386-021-00978-8.
- Mazza, M. G., De Lorenzo, R., Conte, C., Poletti, S., Vai, B., Bollettini, I., Melloni, E., Furlan, R., Ciceri, F., Rovere-Querini, P., COVID-19 BioB Outpatient Clinic Study group, & Benedetti, F. (2020). Anxiety and depression in COVID-19 survivors: Role of inflammatory and clinical predictors. *Brain, behavior, and immunity*, 89, 594–600. doi:10.1016/j.bbi.2020.07.037
- Miskowiak, K.W., Johnsen, S., Sattler, S.M., Nielsen, S., Kunalan, K., Rungby, J., Lapperre, T., & Porsberg, C.M. (2021). Cognitive impairments four months after COVID-19 hospital discharge: Pattern, severity and association with illness variables. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, 46, 39-48. doi:10.1016/j.euroneuro.2021.03.019.
- Salamanna, F., Veronesi, F., Martini, L., Landini, M.P., & Fini, M. (2021). Post-COVID-19 Syndrome: The persistent symptoms at the post-viral stage of the disease. A systematic review of the current data. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 8, 653516. doi:10.3389/fmed.2021.653516
- Sisó-Almirall, A., Brito-Zerón, P., Conangla Ferrín, L., Kostov, B., Moragas Moreno, A., Mestres, J., Sellarès, J., Galindo, G., Morera, R., Basora, J., Trilla, A., & Ramos-Casals, M. (2021). Long Covid-19: Proposed primary care clinical guidelines for diagnosis and disease management. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18, 4350. doi:10.3390/ijerph18084350

World Health Organisation (WHO) – official website:
<https://covid19.who.int/> (09/07/2021)

Xu, F., Wang, X., Yang, Y., Zhang, K., Shi, Y., Xia, L., Hu, X., & Liu, H. (2021). Depression and insomnia in COVID-19 survivors: a cross-sectional survey from Chinese rehabilitation centers in Anhui province. *Sleep medicine*, S1389-9457(21)00093-9. doi:1016/j.sleep.2021.02.002

Appendix I

SCALE OF NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL AND PSYCHIATRIC SYMPTOMS OF THE POST-COVID-19 SYNDROME (SNP-PC19)

Have you experienced any of the problems listed below after suffering from COVID-19 infection? If you have, to what extent did each of them burden you (that is, how pronounced was it)?

To give your answer, please, use the scale from 0 to 4, where the numbers mean:

- 0 – NOT AT ALL (I have not experienced this symptom)
- 1 – POORLY (This symptom has been present to a lesser extent and burdened me poorly)
- 2 – MODERATELY (This symptom has been present moderately and burdened me to some extent)
- 3 – STRONGLY (This symptom has been present to a greater extent and burdened me strongly)
- 4 – VERY STRONGLY (This symptom has been very intense and burdened me very strongly)

Symptom/problem	Not at all	Poorly	Moderately	Strongly	Very strongly
1. problems with concentration/maintenance of attention	0	1	2	3	4
2. problems with memorizing	0	1	2	3	4
3. disorientation/confusion	0	1	2	3	4
4. sleeping problems	0	1	2	3	4
5. difficulties with performing several activities quickly and efficiently at the same time	0	1	2	3	4
6. feelings of sadness	0	1	2	3	4
7. feelings of hopelessness	0	1	2	3	4
8. feelings of disturbance	0	1	2	3	4

9. feelings of anxiety	0	1	2	3	4
10. feelings of fear	0	1	2	3	4
11. tiredness (energy loss)	0	1	2	3	4
12. slow motion (in thinking, speech and/or behaviour)	0	1	2	3	4
13. thoughts about suicide	0	1	2	3	4
14. losing patience/temper easily	0	1	2	3	4
15. frequent and/or sudden mood swings	0	1	2	3	4

Thank you for your time and cooperation!

Appendix II

SKALA NEUROPSIHOLOŠKIH I PSIHIJATRIJSKIH SIMPTOMA POST-COVID-19 SINDROMA (SNP-PC19)

Da li ste doživjeli neki od dolje pobrojanih problema nakon preležane COVID-19 infekcije? Ako jeste, u kojoj mjeri Vas je opterećivao (tj. koliko je bio izražen) svaki od njih?

Molimo Vas da svoj odgovor date na skali od 0 do 4, pri čemu brojevi znače:

- 0 – NIMALO (nisam doživio/doživjela ovaj simptom)
- 1 – SLABO (ovaj simptom (bio) je prisutan u manjoj mjeri i malo me opterećivao)
- 2 – UMJERENO (ovaj simptom (bio) je prisutan u umjerenom mjeri i donekle me opterećivao)
- 3 – JAKO (ovaj simptom (bio) je prisutan u većoj mjeri i jako me opterećivao)
- 4 – VEOMA JAKO (ovaj simptom (bio) je veoma intenzivan i veoma jako me opterećivao)

Simptom/problem	Nimalo	Slabo	Umjereno	Jako	Veoma jako
1. problemi sa koncentracijom/ održavanjem pažnje	0	1	2	3	4
2. problemi sa pamćenjem	0	1	2	3	4
3. dezorijentacija/konfuzija	0	1	2	3	4
4. problemi sa spavanjem	0	1	2	3	4
5. poteškoće sa brzim i efikasnim obavljanjem nekoliko aktivnosti istovremeno	0	1	2	3	4
6. osjećaj tuge	0	1	2	3	4
7. osjećaj beznadežnosti	0	1	2	3	4

8. osjećaj uznemirenosti	0	1	2	3	4
9. osjećaj tjeskobe	0	1	2	3	4
10. osjećaj straha	0	1	2	3	4
11. osjećaj umora (gubitka energije)	0	1	2	3	4
12. usporenost (mišljenja, govora i/ili ponašanja)	0	1	2	3	4
13. misli o samoubistvu	0	1	2	3	4
14. lako/brzo gubljenje strpljenja	0	1	2	3	4
15. učestale i/ili iznenadne promjene raspoloženja	0	1	2	3	4

Hvala Vam na izdvojenom vremenu i saradnji!

**SKALA NEUROPSIHOLOŠKIH I PSIHIJATRIJSKIH SIMPTOMA U OKVIRU POST-COVID-19 SINDROMA (SNP-PC19):
PILOT STUDIJA**

Selman Repišti

Lidija Injac Stevović

Tamara Radojičić

Sažetak

Predstavljamo novo oruđe dizajnirano da mjeri ozbiljnost neuropsiholoških i psihijatrijskih simptoma u okviru tzv. "post COVID-19 sindroma" ili "produženog COVID-19". Oslanjajući se na relevantnu literaturu kao i kliničko iskustvo autora, identificirano je 13 kategorija simptoma. Oni su postali dio instrumenta nazvanog "Skala neuropsiholoških i psihijatrijskih simptoma u okviru post-COVID-19 sindroma" (SNP-PC19). Riječ je o petostepenoj skali Likertovog tipa, čiji je raspon od 0 ("nimalo") to 4 ("veoma jako"), a koja služi kao mjera ozbiljnosti simptoma. SNP-PC19 je primijenjena online, uz nekoliko klinički relevantnih pitanja i pitanja za prikupljanje sociodemografskih podataka ispitanika. Pedeset i četiri ispitanika je ponudilo svoje odgovore a glavno poboljšanje skale odnosilo se na dodavanje dvije stavke: "lako/brzo gubljenje strpljenja" i "učestale i/ili iznenadne promjene

raspoloženja". Dakle, verzija skale nakon pilot studije sadrži 15 tvrdnji. Treba naglasiti da njene psihometrijske karakteristike tek trebaju biti ispitane.

Ključne riječi: post-COVID-19 sindrom, produženi COVID-19, pilot studija, konstrukcija skale, klinička neuropsihologija